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Annotation: *This article enumerates styles of learning language and briefly but clearly explains three given types of learners.*

Key words: *visual learners, kinesthetic learners, auditory learners, learning styles, teachers, represents.*

Aside from the age, culture, and purpose of a class, there's another large aspect which is a little more abstract. When choosing what activities to include in your lesson plans, you should also consider the different ways in which people prefer to learn. There has been a lot of research in the last few decades examining different ways in which people learn. These types of studies are often applicable across different fields, including language learning, and can have an enormously positive effect on your students' understanding and retention of class material. There are a lot of different theories about learning, but a widely recognized belief is that each individual prefers to learn, understand, process and remember new information in a unique way. The ways people prefer to learn are called learning styles, and most people have one preferred learning style, though they can still learn through other styles to lesser degrees. Whether learning styles are genetically or biologically coded, there is a lot of debate on that, but what seems certain is that an individual's learning style will affect how they perform in class. It will also determine their enjoyment of certain classroom activities. To put it simply, if your activities use a learning style that most of your class prefers, then the students that use that learning style will be more engaged, and will do better. Because learning styles are so varied, this means you need to try to include activities from a number of styles to maximize your impact.

The three learning styles that are considered to be the most common are auditory, visual and kinesthetic. These learning styles refer to more than a personal preference. They refer to the way the brain takes in information, and how it best stores and retrieves that information.

Visual learning is defined as the assimilation of information from visual formats. Being visual learner entails thinking in pictures rather than in words. Visual learners learn best by utilizing graphs, tables, charts, maps, colors and diagrams. They also tend to learn holistically instead of sequentially or in parts. Visual learners are good at absorbing information through what they see. They

have many strengths. They are meticulous and highly value planning and organization in their academic living. They are very aware of things like color, brightness, contrast and other visual elements. Talking advantage of these strengths can significantly boost their performance. Another benefits of being a visual learner is easily seeing the big picture. As a result these learners may sometimes miss out on the details.

Auditory learning style enables auditory learners to learn by best hearing or through verbal communication. Auditory learners are good at remembering what they hear as they learn information through auditory representation. Auditory components such as tone, pitch and loudness are all important all those learners. Auditory learners are reported to be excellent listeners. The characteristics of auditory learners include getting information by listening, preferring listening to reading, or writing, having difficulty in communicating through body language and facial expressions, having the ability to reproduce symbols, letters or words by hearing them, finding written directions more difficult to follow than spoken ones. They need to hear something or to speak to know it. Kanar (1995) argued that auditory learners like listening and speaking, have compatible personalities. They are good at telling stories and solving problems in a “talk” way.

“Tell me I forge, teach me I may remember, involve me and I learn”. This famous quote by Benjamin Franklin could be the motto for kinesthetic learners. Kinesthetic learners may be considered active and on the move. They learn best by and can't wait to get going so they can actively explore the world around them. They thrive in an environment where they can see, touch, feel and do to learn. They will enjoy role playing, scenarios, games, benefit from demonstrations and may be able to remember things better when they can associate an action with it. They can inspire others to participate since they are many times the first to dig in and get going on the project. Sometimes kinesthetic learners are misunderstood and appear to be fidgety, distracted or unable to focus when in reality they just can't wait to get started. They are so eager to dig in: listening to all of those directions is just hard and boring.

Almost all learners have different learning strengths that enable them to begin to concentrate, remain focused and understand and remember important information and ideas. They become much more efficient, productive and successful, and it is more probable that they will produce their best work if they manage to apply their strengths.

Teachers are skillful at creating and planning suitable opportunities for school children to progress in learning. Teachers try to encourage learning in their courses, which is good and appropriate for their students and this is a profound approach at a particular time with a particular child or group of children.

Teachers of pupils who learn best using auditory techniques should give oral feedback to their students, rather than a written report. Teacher of visual learners should be creative because creativity is key for a visual spatial learner and they should allow students to represent their learning in visual and creative ways. In order to teach kinesthetic learners teachers should be fulfilled with energy because they are active learners who learn with playing, touching and practical.

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